

Requirements and Best Practices in Research Data Management (RDM) at the University of Basel and the Faculty of Psychology

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1 Introduction and definitions

1.1 Requirements and best practices in RDM

This document contains requirements and best practices for research data management at the University of Basel, and specifically at the Faculty of Psychology of the University of Basel.

1.2 Definitions

Research data management refers to all activities and decisions along the life cycle of research data, from planning to collecting and analyzing, storing and preserving to publishing and sharing and discovering and reusing data.

Requirements are binding rules for members of the University of Basel.

Best practices are proven general or domain specific recommendations.

All other definitions can be found in the [Glossary of the RDM website](#).

1.3 Target audience

Generally, the target audience of these information are researchers at the Faculty of Psychology at the University of Basel (PI, PhD students, data owner, research groups, chair leaders etc.)

1.4 Purpose

The purpose of this information on best practices in RDM is to provide a quick overview of best practices in RDM in general, and specifically in Psychology with links to helpful tools and information material. Additionally, the idea is to motivate researchers to establish their specific best practices.

The order of the document corresponds to the phases of the following research data life cycle:

2 Plan & Fund

2.1 Roles and Responsibilities in RDM

Requirement	Clarify roles and responsibilities
Best Practice	Clarify roles and responsibilities prior to the beginning of a research project to avoid problems and delays during research.

The roles and responsibilities in RDM at the University of Basel are based on the [Policy on research data management at the University of Basel](#) (only available in German).

Responsibilities for principal investigators (PI), researchers	
Implementation of data management	Implement research data management in research groups and continuously validate and – if necessary – adapt the implantation.
Data Management Plan	Creation of a data management plan (DMP) for the entire research project at the beginning of a research project.
Retention, storage and archiving	Clarify responsibilities for retention, storage and archiving of research data at the beginning of research project. Alignment with the requirements of the funding organizations and the University of Basel (the academic integrity regulation mandates a minimum of 5-year retention period).
Storage, annotation, archiving	Contact relevant service providers for storage , annotation , and archiving , addressing project-specific requirements (e.g., large storage needs, security, international collaborations) at an early phase of research project.
Legal and ethical issues	Ensure legal and ethical compliance for research data processing, obtaining approvals from relevant authorities (e.g., Cantonal Ethics Commission , University Ethics Committee , Data Protection Officer University of Basel or Canton).
Documentation	Document continuously according to "Best Practice" in the research field (e.g., ELNs , code repositories) to ensure work and data are understandable, traceable, and ideally reusable post-project.
Long-term archiving, data transfer	Consider and address the options and requirements for long-term archiving or data transfer well in advance when planning for a change in positions or approaching retirement.

Responsibilities for supervisors of students (master's and doctoral levels)	
Education in Research Data management	Provide opportunities on a regular basis for acquiring necessary knowledge and skills, such as training courses or integrating data management into daily research activities in institutes, groups, and labs.

Leaders of institutes	
Implementation of data management	Implement on a regular basis research data management in units, ensuring staff know university policies and get support. Also clarify post-project data access for departing employees.

Best Practice **Think about the end at the beginning:** Plan your end-of-project data management strategy early in the project planning process.

The RDM Network provides general [guidelines and a checklist on how to manage digital research data at the end of a project](#).

2.2 RDM support

Best Practice Let research data management be part of your research right from the start of your project and reach out for support.

Visit the [RDM website of the Faculty of Psychology](#) or/and contact the [data steward](#) for specific RDM support early in the project planning/application stage.

Contact the [RDM Network coordination team](#) for general RDM support at the University of Basel.

2.3 Data Management Plan

Best Practice Start drafting your **Data Management Plan (DMP)** as a living document as early as possible.

Almost all research funders require the submission of a DMP together with the project application or as soon as the project is approved. Clarify the requirements of your research funder early on when writing your application.

The Faculty of Psychology provides an instance of the [Research Data Management Organizer \(RDMO\)](#) that supports research projects in the planning, implementation and administration of all research data management tasks. It is primarily a tool for creating and maintaining a data management plan (DMP), whereby various templates for a DMP can be selected, which can also be adapted to your project.

Treat the DMP as a living document and update it regularly during the project as well as at the end of the project.

For further information and DMP templates, see: [Data Management Plan on the RDM website](#)

2.4 Determining costs of RDM

Best practice	Consider cost planning for RDM as early as the project planning/ application stage.
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See the UK data service for an [example of a checklist for assessing costs of RDM](#).

2.5 Approval by ethics committees

Requirement	Certain research projects must be approved by ethics committees.
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Useful tools and advice providers for assessing whether approval by an ethics committee is required:

- [Ethics committee of the Faculty of Psychology](#) of the University of Basel

2.6 Regulation on research with personal data

Requirement	Research with personal data must be lawful.
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For further information and advice providers at the University of Basel for research with personal data, see:

- [Data Stewards at the University of Basel as first point of contact](#)
- [Data Protection Office](#)
- [Legal and personal rights issues in RDM](#)
- [Checklist on how to deal with personal data in research](#)
- [Ethics committee of the Faculty of Psychology](#)

2.7 Intellectual Property Rights

Requirement	Research must be compliant with copyright law.
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For further information and advice providers at the University of Basel, see:

- [Intellectual property rights in RDM](#)
- [Legal Services](#)
- [Unitectra](#)

2.8 Data collection planning

Best Practice	Carefully plan which data need to be newly collected and which data already exist and can potentially be reused.
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Instructions on how to organize newly collected data: see next paragraph on [Collect and Analyze](#).

Useful information on how to discover, cite and reuse already existing research data: see Paragraph on [Discover and Reuse](#).

2.9 Preregistration of a study

Best Practice	Register methodological approach and study design with which the research question/hypothesis is to be answered before the actual data collection.
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Preregistrations can counteract to both scientific as well as publication bias (bias of research in favor of positive findings).

Detailed information:

- [Kienbaum, J., & Jacob, B. \(2023\). FDM-Portfolio Psychologie und Bildungsforschung: Disziplinspezifische Dienste, Praktiken & Leitlinien für das Forschungsdatenmanagement \(page 11 f\)](#)
- [Workshop reader](#) on reregistration processes provided by the IQB Berlin (in German)

Registries and Templates:

- [OSF Registries](#) of the data platform Open Science Framework (OSF)
 - [Step-by-step instructions](#) for using the OSF for preregistration
 - [Public template](#) for preregistration in Social Psychology
- [PreReg](#) platform provided by Leibniz Institute for Psychology, where preregistrations are archived in [PsychArchives](#) repository with a time stamp and persistent identifier
- [Preregistration Standards for Psychology - the Psychological Research Preregistration-Quantitative \(aka PRP-QUANT\) Template](#)
- The Center for Open Science (COS) offers a list of journals that allow submission of preregistration-based [Registered Reports](#) that allow peer review prior to data collection
- [Prospero](#) for clinical systematic reviews / meta analyses (Preregistration and database of ongoing studies)

2.10 Personal persistent identifier

Best Practice

Set up a personal persistent identifier (PID) to improve the recognizability and findability of you and your research results.

Persistent identifiers:

Persistent identifiers allow scientists and repositories to uniquely identify persons or cite datasets (see [6.2 Data Citation](#) for more examples).

ORCID: Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier:

- Is globally recognized.
- Provides individual researchers with a unique and free digital identifier, which can be used throughout one's career, regardless of job changes, new funding sources, or variations in name.
- Improves recognition and discoverability for you and your research outputs and is interoperable working with many institutions, funders, and publishers.

NOTE: The SNSF no longer requires a list of publications, but only the ORCID, in grant applications.

3 Collect & Analyze

3.1 IT tools and infrastructure for research and handling of data

Requirement	Comply with the obligations arising from the university's regulations regarding the use of IT tools and infrastructure and the handling of data.
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The University of Basel published [regulations on the use of IT tools and infrastructure](#):

- [Regulation on the acceptable use of IT resources](#)
 - Particular attention should be paid to the Guiding principle (§5.), to the Use of private IT devices (§6.) and to Data protection and information security (§7.).
- [Informationssicherheitsordnung](#)
- [Weisung des Rektorats betreffend Verwaltung persönlicher Zugangsberechtigungen zu universitären Informatikmitteln](#)

Faculty of Psychology

The IT department of the [Faculty of Psychology](#) supports staff and students in digital, web-based and technical matters. Several regulations apply:

- [Terms of Use IT resources of the Faculty of Psychology](#) (German)
- [General terms of use for virtual machines](#) (German)
- [Information about the data backup systems of the Faculty of Psychology](#) (Backup system)
- [Documents and Applications](#)

3.2 Data and file organization

Best practice	Choose a logical and consistent file organization and naming convention. This will help you and your colleagues to find files easily.
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For further information, see: [Data and file organization on the RDM website](#)

Strings for file naming:

It will be helpful to include the following strings in a file name:

- Project (abbreviation)
- Author (whole name or initials)
- Description of the content
- Date (YYYY-MM-DD) / Version
- Research Team / Department

Make sure that the terms are as short, clear and understandable as possible for outsiders. Please keep in mind that not all characters are allowed for folder and file naming. We recommend that you do not exceed a path length of 260 characters and use only the following characters:

(ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZabcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz0123456789-_)

Folder structure (example):

For recommendations by the Faculty of Psychology, see:

- File naming conventions: [Information über die Datensicherungssysteme der Fakultät der Psychologie](#) (Backup system, German)

Readme Files

Adding a readme file to folders or datasets is a simple way of explaining and documenting what is in the folder. A readme file is a simple text file on the first hierarchy level of the dataset. For more information, see the [RDM website on Documentation](#).

3.3 File formats

Best practice

Choose file formats that ensure easy accessibility and inter-operability for long lasting use of research data.

Choose file formats that:

- have no licenses
- are readable by many software products (at best by open source/code software)
- have no encryption or digital rights management (DRM)
- are established in your research community
- have open accessible documentation

The following is a list of [recommended file formats](#).

Data Type	recommended	also possible
plain text	UTF-8	
text	PDF/A-2, DOCX, ODT, OTT	RTF, PDF
table ¹	PDF/A-2, XLSX, XLSM, ODS, OTS	PDF, CSV, (legacy: XLC, XLW, XLM)
presentation	PDF/A-2, PPTX, ODP, OTP	PDF
images /raster graphs	JPEG 2000 Part 1 (lossless compressed)	TIFF, EXIF Image, JPEG, PNG, DNG, BMP, ODG
vector graphs	SVG (without script bindings)	
audio	WAVE LPCM (uncompressed), BWF	MP3, FLAC, AIFF, AIFC, OGG, MPEG-4, WMA, AAC, MIDI, AU, M4A, EXIF Audio
video / film	Matroska/FFV1.3 (Videocodec ffv1 v3, GOP-size 1; Audiocodec: pcm_s16le; in MKV Matroska container); MPEG-4 Part 10 (Videocodec: h.264, 8Bit, 4:2:0 Chroma Subsampling; Audiocodec: aac; in MP4 container)	AVI, Quick Time Movie, MPEG 1, MPEG 2, WMV, VOB
data base ²	SIARD	SQL-Dump, XML, HDF5
hypertext / websites	PDF/A-2, HTML, WARC	PDF
E-mail	PDF/A-2	MBOX, EML

For formats for medical data, see: [Electroencephalography - Brain Imaging Data Structure v1.9.0 \(bids-specification.readthedocs.io\)](#)

¹ The format selection for tables depends on the preservation of the functionality. Under certain circumstances (e.g. with formulas or macros) it is necessary to deviate from the recommended formats.

² Alternative to the conversion of SQL / XML into SIARD via SIARD Suite (BAR): [DaSCH](#) for more complex and often to be used data objects.

3.4 Data and code version control

Best practice

Label every file version logically and consistently.

⇒ Use code version control by deploying
<https://gitlab.psychologie.unibas.ch/>

For GitLab you need to **submit a request** to the [web administration of the Faculty of Psychology](#).

4 Preserve & Store

4.1 Storage

Requirement	Store your data at least during 5 years after publication of the research results (University of Basel). ⇒ Some research funders might require or recommend longer periods of data retention.
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The University of Basel requires data must be available upon request at least 5 years after publication of the research results (see [Regulation relating to academic integrity at the University of Basel, Art. 4, 8](#)).

Some research sponsors recommend longer data retention; for example, [the SNSF recommends 10 years](#).

All data relating to clinical trials must be retained for at least twenty years after completion or premature termination of the clinical trial ([Ordinance on Clinical Trials, ClinO, Art. 45](#)).

For storage solutions and best practices concerning storage at the University of Basel, see the [RDM website on Storage](#).

- Active storage
- Deep storage
- Preservation / archiving
- Selecting research data
- Recommended file formats for medium- to long-term readability of data

Storage solutions and best practices concerning storage at the Faculty of Psychology:

- [Research data storage, Faculty of Psychology, University of Basel](#)
- [Research IT, Quicklinks, Faculty of Psychology, University of Basel](#)

4.2 Documentation and Metadata

Best practice	Document your research and annotate metadata.
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For general information on documentation and metadata, see:

- [RDM website on Documentation](#)

Documentation platform of the Faculty of Psychology:

- [Research documentation Confluence](#)

4.3 Data deletion

Requirement	Decide regularly which data can be deleted and delete.
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Deleting unnecessary data helps reduce storage usage. Keep data that support research outcomes and conclusions, enable research integrity and reproducibility, have potential for reuse (e.g. in future research or teaching), and comply with ethical, legal and regulatory requirements. For more information on data security, see the [requirements by IT services of the University of Basel](#).

Special case: If you have data on teaching platforms such as ADAM, EvaExam or Panopto, follow the [guidelines provided by IT services](#) (in German).

4.4 Data long-term preservation/archiving

Best practice	Decide whether your research data will be preserved/archived in the long-term (100+ years) and how.
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For more information on long-term preservation/archiving, see the [RDM website on Storage](#).

5 Publish & Share

5.1 Data access and sharing with internal or external collaborators

Requirement	Clarify data sharing and transfer with Unitectra , data protection office (DPO) and IT Psychology . Establish a data transfer and/or processing agreement between e.g. your research group and external collaborators as soon as possible.
Best practice	PI and data owner should consider and document as early as project planning/application as well as regularly during research process: ⇒ who is allowed to access which data and for how long (confidentiality agreements might be applicable) And inform IT Psychology about data access management and report changes.

Data access and sharing in this case refers to you **sharing data with internal or external collaborators and researchers during an ongoing research project**. In the case of data sharing with external partners, agreements must be set up and data must either be transferred or a storage solution must be selected that is also accessible to people outside the University of Basel.

If you want to share data within the University of Basel, consider appropriate [data storage](#), [data transfer solutions](#) and [data access regulations](#).

If you reuse existing data (e.g. from the hospital or from another university) in your research project, please see the explanations in paragraph [6.5 Agreements and Contracts for Data Transfer and Reuse](#). In that paragraph you will also find more details on Data Transfer Agreements (DTA) and research contracts as well as points of contact, which are also relevant for data sharing.

5.2 Publication of research data on repositories

Requirement	Comply with legal regulations and take ethical considerations into account when publishing and sharing research data.
Best practice	Make the data that support your findings available to the research community by publishing your research data on a repository. + Publish your data according to the FAIR principles , which many funders require.

For more information, see the RDM website on [Publishing](#).

The Faculty of Psychology also provides a list of [recommended repositories](#).

5.3 End of project and agreement with project leader/management

Best practice

Establish an agreement between e.g. every research group member and the project leader about data access and usage when offboarding (leaving the research group or University of Basel etc.)

The RDM Network of the University of Basel provides general [guidelines and a checklist on how to manage digital research data at the end of a project](#).

6 Discover & Reuse

6.1 Finding Data

Best practice	Use repositories, search engines and/or data journals to find relevant research data.
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- **Research data repositories:**
 - Specialized online platforms (domain-specific, interdisciplinary or institutional) where research data can be uploaded and shared together with the related metadata.
 - To find [repositories](#) you can use [re3data](#) (Registry of Research Data Repositories) and filter e.g. for subject-specific repositories.
 - The Faculty of Psychology also provides [a list of recommended repositories](#).
 - also see [5.1 Publication of research data on repositories](#)
- **Meta search engines:**
 - Enable simultaneous retrieval of several research data repositories. Examples for meta search engines are [DataCite Commons](#), [OpenAire Explore](#), [Google Dataset Search](#), [Mendeley Data](#) or [b2find.eudat.eu](#).
- **Data journals:**
 - Articles in data journals provide extensive information about a dataset. Unlike "typical" scientific journals, they do not interpret the data but provide a rich description of a dataset. A [list of data journals](#) is provided by [forschungsdaten.org](#).

6.2 Data Citation

Best practice	When reusing a dataset, cite the data and give credit to the original data creator(s).
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Data citation increases transparency and is generally good scientific practice. The citation should include the following information about the dataset:

- Author(s)
- Title of the dataset
- Year of publication
- Repository
- Version (if indicated)
- Persistent Identifier

Example for the citation of a dataset:

Krasselt, J., & Dreesen, P. (2024). Topic model and n-grams for islamophobic blog PI-News (Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. LaRS - Language Repository of Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.48656/k36g-aq92>.

Persistent identifiers (PID):

PID are a long-lasting reference to a digital resource. PID allow scientists and repositories to uniquely identify e.g. persons, publications or data objects. Examples of widely used PID include:

- **DOI: Digital Object Identifier** (Unique alphanumeric string assigned by a registration agency (e.g. DataCite, Crossref) to identify content and provide a persistent link to its location on the Internet)
- **ARK ID: Archival Resource Key Identifier** (particularly useful for hierarchically structured data objects)
- **ORCID: Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier** (Provides an identifier for authors as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities)

6.3 Reuse of datasets

Requirement	Clarify the terms and conditions under which you are authorized to reuse the data, including licenses.
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Determine who compiled the data to assess the **reliability of the source**.

Assess **data quality** by:

- Confirming the data comes from a trusted, curated source.
- Ensuring it adheres to relevant standards.

Ensure **sufficient metadata** for data reuse, as some datasets require extensive metadata for proper interpretation.

Verify **ethical data collection** and compliance with applicable **policies and regulations**.

Review and understand **dataset licenses** to ensure proper access, sharing, and reuse in compliance with legal and ethical standards. In cases where no license is provided, researchers should seek clarification from the data provider or assume that reuse is restricted.

6.4 Reuse of datasets containing personal data

Requirement	Legal and technical obligations must be satisfied before personal data can be accessed.
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Review useful tools and advice providers in [2.5 Regulation on research with personal data](#).

Comply with **repository guidelines**, or **contact the PI** of the research project or the respective **Data Access Committee** of the institution to request access to the data.

Check in particular if an **informed consent** has been obtained in the previous project, if it is still valid and if it covers the reuse of the data in your project. Additionally, check whether a **general consent** has been obtained, as it may cover the reuse of data for research purposes without requiring a new informed consent.

Data collected during hospitalizations and ambulant visits at the University Hospital: Contact the Data Governance Board of the hospital. For more information see their [Documentation on handling personal data](#) (in German).

Data under the governance of the Medical Faculty: Contact the [Data Access Committee of the Medical Faculty \(MF-DAC\)](#) to find out which requirements you have to meet to get access to the data.

Be aware that in most cases the data has to be deleted again. Be sure that you are able to comply with all requirements.

6.5 Agreements and Contracts for Data Transfer and Reuse

Requirement	To transfer and reuse data from another project, researchers must set up a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) or a research contract with the data provider.
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When sharing research data externally, it's crucial to distinguish between a **Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)**, which governs data use, confidentiality, and protection without financial or collaborative obligations, and a **research contract**, which covers broader cooperation, including funding and intellectual property. For example, sharing anonymized survey data requires a DTA, while a joint funded study needs a research contract.

- DTAs on non-personal data are managed by [Unitectra](#). For DTAs on personal data, directly consult the [Data Protection Officer \(DPO\)](#).
- According to the University of Basel's [guidelines concerning contract flow](#) all research contracts must be evaluated by a specialist office, depending on the research topic. Research contracts for the Faculty of Psychology are managed by [Unitectra](#), which involves the [DPO](#) for data protection-relevant content. For funded projects, involve the [Grants Office](#). For research contracts below CHF 50,000, the project lead and the research group lead / department lead sign the contract. For research contracts exceeding CHF 50,000, the [Vice President's Office for Research](#) must approve and sign the agreement. The contract should be entered into the [Grants Tool](#) after legal evaluation at the latest, but before signing.

Engaging the aforementioned offices ensures compliance with legal, ethical and institutional requirements.

At the start of your project (or if you are joining an already running project), **clarify if DTAs or research contracts already exist** for the project you want to work on. Adhere to all agreements made.

**University
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7 Glossary

Descriptions of terms used in this document can be found in the [glossary of the RDM Network website](#).